
FEATURES OF THE STUDENT'S MENTAL ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted about mental education which is defined as an important aspect of preparing a person for life and work. In addition, discusses characteristic features of mental development and classification of mental activity proposed by scientists.

Keywords: *mental education, mental activity, intellectual activity, mental development, creative thinking, teaching methods.*

In pedagogy, mental education is defined as an important aspect of preparing a person for life and work. Its essence is to stimulate interest in intellectual activity, to guide the intellect and cognitive abilities through the introduction of a culture of intellectual labor, the methods of acquiring and acquiring knowledge and applying it in practice.

Research in pedagogy and psychology has two important concepts for understanding the problem of mental education. One of them is the acquisition of knowledge accumulated by people in the process of teaching. This view has been developed by most representatives of philosophy and pedagogy since the time of Plato (Y.A.Komenskiy, J.Lokk, I.F.Herbert, etc.). Representatives of this concept were based on the social experience of mankind in defining mental education. This, of course, was a positive aspect of the concept. But the concept took into account the capabilities, needs and interests of students [1].

Other proponents of the concept (J.J.Russo and his followers) argue that the child's mind develops first of all in its natural activity. The student must be given the opportunity to work, to move, to be independent. Science is secondary. This concept has both positive and negative aspects.

The idea of mental education in the process of active independent activity is positive, but it is not enough to look at it as a single rule. There is no denying that science has accumulated and systematized human experiences.

Proponents of pragmatism have strongly criticized the concept of systematized learning. Dj.Dewey argues that the development, life, and experience of the individual in school are subject to curricula that need to be studied and that define the scope of systematic knowledge because they are dead, mechanical, and formal sources. He calls for the abandonment of the "school science" tradition and the introduction of an "artificial process" in teaching.

In the process of developing mental education, an attempt has been made to enrich this concept. K.D.Ushinskiy [5] believes that the mind can be developed both formally and realistically. This means that different approaches, in close connection with the existing relationship to mental development, allow us to look at the die.

A person's actual relationship is his or her attitude toward nature, society, and the arts. In this regard, it is important to master the science that has been accumulated and systematized over the centuries of human experience. It is necessary not only to acquire knowledge, but also to delve into its essence, to learn how to acquire and apply it, to turn knowledge into a tool of faith, thinking and action.

Mental development is determined not only by the amount and quality of knowledge acquisition, but also by the structure of the thought process, the richness of logical practice and mental action, and its proper application. A general condition of mental education is comprehensive activity. The nature of the activity is also important. Mental development is intensified as the scientific foundations on which it is based expand. It is the opposite of being idle and wasting time. It creates intellectual weakness, backwardness.

The main processes of mental development are covered in the research of L.S.Vigodskiy, S.L.Rubinstein, A.N.Leontev, N.A.Menchinskaya, L.V.Zankov, M.A.Danilov, B.P.Yesinov, M.N.Skatkin. They emphasize that mental development is a continuous process of learning, work, play, and improvement in life situations.

Mental development is very intensive in the process of active acquisition and creative application of knowledge.

Characteristic features of mental development include:

- *be proactive about the environment;*
- *striving to go beyond what is known;*
- *the constant need to increase knowledge and apply it creatively for theoretical and practical purposes;*
- *observation, the ability to distinguish the most important aspects and connections of events and facts;*

- consistency of actions and research to provide a link between the tasks and tools needed to solve problems rationally;
- discipline that ensures accuracy in work and reliability in achieving results;
- mental breadth is a product quality based on the sequence of mental activity and memory development;
- ability to rely on extensive scientific information;
- ability to use a wide range of scientific, technical and computer tools;
- a tendency to learn and use concepts that continuously reflect real-life processes;
- dynamics of mental activity;
- independence and creative character.

The highest form of developed mind is creative thinking. It is the stage of human cognition and the highest form of the process of reflecting objective reality. Creative thinking acquires social significance and uniqueness as the highest form of activity and individual activity. *It is a question that requires a creative response; be able to see the problem; mobilize the knowledge needed to identify preconceived hypotheses and problem-solving methods; reflects the expression of ideas born as a result of special observations and experiments.*

For the advanced mind, a logical thinking consisting of a careful analysis of the situation on the basis of the observed facts and a logic-based synthesis is characteristic.

According to G.Selyevko [6], thinking refers to the processes of human cognition in the perception of objects in the environment, events, connections between them, the solution of vital tasks, the search for the unknown, the ability to see the future. The classification of mental activity proposed by G.Selyevko is as follows:

- depending on the nature of the means of thinking: object, action, visual, figurative, abstract, emotional;
- according to the process of the logical scheme: comparison, analysis, abstraction, generalization, synthesis, classification, induction, deduction, inversion, reflection, anticipation, hypothesis, experiment, etc .;
- according to the result: the creation of a new model, the definition of a concept, a judgment, a conclusion, a theorem, a law, a law, theory;
- by type of logical thinking: mental-emotional and perceptual-theoretical or, as defined by M.V.Davidov, dialectical-logical.

I.S.Yakimanskaya [7] developed "teaching methods". This concept covers the area of the qualification process that determines the effectiveness of the learning process. Based on this, the general teaching methods of work are distinguished:

- *learning planning skills;*
- *skills and abilities to organize educational activities;*
- *information comprehension skills;*
- *thinking skills;*
- *ability to evaluate and understand learning outcomes.*

In the classification proposed by G.Selyevko [6], knowledge is distinguished by the form of reflection, the delimitation of illumination, the field and subject of knowledge, the level of psychological and generalization.

Depending on the reflection range, the following can be distinguished:

- individual knowledge - a set of emotional and mental images and their interrelationships that arise in relation to reality, its personal experience, work and knowledge of the world;
- social knowledge is the product of environmental generalizations and cognitive outcomes reflected in science, technology, material and spiritual values.

Depending on the form of reflection:

- sign, verbal knowledge or theoretical knowledge;
- figurative - knowledge perceived in the senses and recommended in the emblems;
- material - knowledge of labor, art;
- event - knowledge recorded in the current activities of people.

There are the following areas of study:

Humanities and exact mathematical sciences philosophy philosophy animate and inanimate nature society, technology, art.

Depending on the psychological level, there are: familiarity, recovery, understanding, application, automatic action, attitude and knowledge - the need.

According to the level of generalization, facts - events, concepts, terms, laws, hypotheses - theories, methodological knowledge, evaluation.

Thus, understanding can be assessed by the features of mental operations, strategies for finding solutions, volume, depth, clarity, time required to find a positive result of solving a problem. An error is a necessary element of learning activity, therefore, it must be detected in time, identified and measured. Its timely recognition

involves the activation of mental activity, contributes to the formation of cognitive subjective experience and school success.

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